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FOOD ANALYSIS AND DIETARY DIVERSITY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN (6 MONTHS – 5 YEARS) DIETS IN THREE INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS CAMPS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Internal Displaced Persons are persons or group of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, as a result of avoiding the effects of armed conflict, violence, violation of human rights, natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized State border while Preschool age child is a child who is not yet attending a

public or private kindergarten school program, they are more vulnerable as any adverse influence on them during this period may result in limitation in their physical and mental development, some of which may be irreversible. Nutritional problems among preschool children can cause major health challenges. The objective of this study is to analyze the food and dietary diversity of preschool children's diets in three internally displaced people's camps in three geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Questionnaires were used to obtain information on socio-demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the index children in the households at New Kunchigoro IDP camp Abuja, Bakasi camp in Borno and Bakassi camp in Bayelsa. Research assistants were recruited and trained on the method of questionnaire administration. A total number of 1,420 questionnaires were distributed & all retrieved. These were collated and sorted for accuracy & completeness before leaving the field each day. Food samples were collected from the caregivers to analyze for the nutritive values of (protein, fat, carbohydrate, dietary fibre, ash, Iron and calcium). The research was carried out on 1,420 (100%) children of 6 to 59 months who are the target group; it was observed that 280 (20%) were less than 12 months of age, and 1,010 (71%) were 2nd to 4th born children of the family. The dietary diversity of the 1,420 preschools diets shows that 441 (31.0%) preschool children consumed less than 4 food groups in 24 hours, while 509 (35.8%) consumed 5 food groups, 446 (31.4%) of the respondents consumed 6 food groups, while 24 (1.6%) consumed more than more than 7 food groups. The Mean Nutrient present in each food sample indicates 62.03 moisture, 2.52 Ash, 1.08 Dietary fiber, 6.81 fat, 6.39 protein, 21.19 carbon, 0.05 iron, 3.36 calcium and 181.36 energy. Data entry and processing were done using the determination of proximate compositions of the food samples described in AOAC (2015) (Association of Official Analytical Chemists). The study revealed that internally displaced persons in Nigeria experience extreme challenges in the form of lack of good shelter, food, clothing, rape, threat of death from violence or conflict, forced conscription of children into armed groups, insecurities and basic amenities such as health, nutrition, water, sanitation, hygiene, diseases and even deaths. And malnutrition remains a major health problem among under-five children in internal displaced camps with prevalence of underweight, stunting and wasting at 42.0%, 41.0% and 29.3%, respectively. The key determinants of malnutrition in this population include age, birth order, gender and deworming status.

KEY WORDS: Food, Dietary, Diversity, Preschool, Displaced

INTRODUCTION

An internally displaced person is someone who is forced to leave their home but who remains within their country's borders and have not crossed to another country, they are on the run at home. IDPs stay within their own country and remain under the protection of its government; they are among the most vulnerable group of people in the world. In Nigeria, there has been forceful displacement by Boko Haram Islamists leading to effects on their social, political and economic status. The insurgency carried by the sect in the Northern States of Nigeria accounts for over 90 percent of the IDPs, and less than 10 percent caused by natural disasters in Nigeria, like flood, land dispute, etc, (Abimbola and Adesote, 2012). This situation stemmed from the insurgency by the Boko Haram sect leading to the rising number of deaths of innocent citizens, in the States of Adamawa, Borno and Yobe as well as rendering others refugees in foreign countries of Cameroun, Chad, and Niger republics, (Ibeanu, 2015).

It is very difficult to get accurate figures for IDPs because populations are not constant. IDPs may be returning home while others are fleeing, others may periodically return to IDP camps to take

advantage of humanitarian aid (Mooney, 2003). Conflicts and disasters often cause large-scale displacement of people due to destruction of homes and environment, religious or political persecution or economic necessity. One of the contemporary challenges facing the Nigerian states is how to provide succor to the plights of the internally displaced persons, occasioned by incessant violent attacks in some part of the country, many lives have been lost while properties worth millions of naira have been destroyed, forcing many people to flee their homes for safer areas, (Lenshie and Ayokhai, 2011). Obviously, the most affected persons are the vulnerable groups such as children, aged and women who are exposed to severe socioeconomic and political challenges. The local and government humanitarian assistance given to IDPs are inadequate, especially on food and nutrition. Sometimes the host communities are likely to become less hospitable the longer an IDP crisis lasts. Most IDP crises occur in the poorest regions of the world, with immense material hardship experienced by the IDPs (Holzer 2012).

Adequate diet is one of the most important and modifiable life-style determinants of human health, whereas under-nutrition plays role in morbidity & mortality in human life, more alarming on the preschool children. Adequate nutrition is needed to reduce the rate of health risks through dietary changes (Rao, Yadav, Dolla, Kumar, Bhondeley and Ukey, 2005).

There is therefore the need for Substantial studies, in relation to the level of nutrition provided locally and nationally in Nigeria IDP Camps to address the poor health and nutritional status existing in the camps as well as develop relevant strategies to improving the food supply to the IDPs in the camps.

METHODOLOGY

The Internally Displaced Persons camps studied were the New Kunchingoro IDP camp in Abuja (North Central), Bakasi IDP Camp in Borno (North East) and Bakassi IDP camp in Bayelsa (South South)

To achieve the objectives of this study, the following procedure was followed.

- **Study Design and Population**

The selected number of IDP camps was arrived at by using a descriptive cross-sectional concept, a minimum sample of 1,420 preschool children were determined. The study population was comprised of the caregivers or mothers with children between 6 months to 5 years who have resided in their camps for a minimum of three years and were available in the camps during the period of the study. While, children and caregivers who just visited the camp at the time of this study were excluded

Indexed children aged 6 to 59 months and their caregivers were selected from the three sampled IDP camps using simple random sampling technique. Nutrition education was given to the caregivers, which was continued as the care givers were returning from their jobs

- **Data collection**

Questionnaires were used to obtain information on socio-demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the index children in the households at New Kunchigoro IDP camp Abuja, Bakasi camp in Borno and Bakassi camp in Bayelsa, research assistants were recruited and trained on the method of questionnaire administration. A total number of 1,420 questionnaires were distributed & all retrieved these were, collated and sorted out for accuracy & completeness before leaving the

field each day. Food samples were collected from the caregivers to analyze for the nutritive values for (protein, fat, carbohydrate, dietary fibre, ash, Iron and calcium).

The questionnaires were pre-tested at the Ox-Bow lake IDP camp in Bayelsa State with 50 respondents and necessary amendments were made. A total number of 1,420 questionnaires were distributed & all retrieved, collated and sorted for accuracy & completeness before leaving the field each day. Food analysis was done through the following analysis

Proximate and Mineral Analysis: The method used in the determination of proximate compositions of the food samples is described in AOAC (2015) (Association of Official Analytical Chemists).

Determination of Ash Content: One (1) gram of each sample was weighed into a crucible of known weight in triplicates, ignited over a Bunsen burner and ashed in a muffle furnace at 600⁰C for 2hours. The crucible was cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The percentage of ash content was thus calculated as;

$$\% \text{ AshContent} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

Where;

W₁ = weight of empty crucible

W₂ = weight of crucible + Ash

Determination of Crude Fat Content: Crude fat content was determined using the Soxhlet extraction method. A 250ml Soxhlet flask was weighed, washed and dried in an oven at 105⁰c for 30minutes, then cooled in desiccators and weighed. Ten (10) grams of each of each sample was weighed into a clean extracting thimble and covered with a cotton wool. The Soxhlet extractor was assembled and placed on a heating mantle. Fat extraction lasted for 3hours. After 3hours, the extractor was disassembled and the solvent was distilled off and recovered. The crude fat left in the flask was dried in the oven at 100⁰c for 30minutes and placed in the desiccator to cool to room temperature. The flask was then weighed. The percentage crude fat content was thus calculated as;

$$\% \text{ FatContent} = \frac{\text{Weight of fat extracted}}{\text{Weight of food Sample}} \times 100$$

Determination of Crude Protein Content: The percentage protein content was computed from the nitrogen content as determined by the micro-kjeldahl method, multiplied by a conversion factor (AOAC, 2015). One (1) gram of each sample was weighed into an ashless filter paper, wrapped carefully and placed into a clean micro-kjeldahl digestion flask. Then 20ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added to the sample. A small quantity of copper sulphate was also added as a catalyst. The flask was then placed on a digestion mantle and gently heated until frothing ceased. It was later heated more vigorously with periodic shaking until a clear solution was obtained. The digest was cooled and washed into the kjeldahl distilling flask with 100ml ammonia, free distilled water and some anti-bumping granules were added. The distillation apparatus was set up and the solution in the flask was distilled into a 10ml of 4% Boric acid solution containing three (3) drops

of mixed indicator methyl-red and bromo-cresol green. A total of 50ml distillate was collected and titrated against 0.02 H₂SO₄ solutions. The distillate process was also carried out on a blank sample. The end point of filtration was marked by a colour change to point. The percentage crude protein was thus calculated as;

$$\% \text{ Crude Protein} = \frac{V_E - V_b \times N_a \times 0.0014 \times 6.25}{M} \times 100$$

Where;

V_E = Titre value for the sample distillate

V_b = Titre value for the blank distillate

N_a = Normality of titrate/ acid used

0.0014 = Conversion constant for % Nitrogen

6.25 = Conversion constant from Nitrogen to Protein

M = Weight of Test Sample (g)

Determination of Moisture Content: The percentage moisture content was determined using the two-stage air-oven method. Two (2) grams of each of the sample was weighed into dried aluminum crucibles of known weights (W₁ and W₂) and then placed in an air oven. The sample was heated and dried at 130°C for one hour. After drying, the crucibles were cooled to room temperature and re-weighed (W₃). The process was repeated until a constant weight was obtained. The percentage moisture content was thus calculated as;

$$\% \text{ Moisture Content} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100$$

Where;

W₁ = weight of empty crucible

W₂ = weight of sample + crucible before drying

W₃ = weight of sample + crucible after drying

Dietary fibre determination: The total dietary fibre (TDF), Insoluble dietary fibre (IDF) and soluble dietary fibre (SDF) were determined using the enzymatic-gravimetric method as described by (FAO/WHO, 2017).

The total dietary fibre was determined as follow:

Gelatinization of starch: About 10ml of distilled water were pipette into the 50mls beaker containing 1g of each defatted dried sample. The water and the sample contained in each 50mls beaker were stirred thoroughly to obtain a homogenous mixture. Water was poured into a water bath and the samples were placed on it, with the help of steam from the water bath, the starch in the samples gelatinized at 100°C

Termamyl incubation: After the starch gelatinization, the samples were ready for termamyl incubation. This was done at pH 6.0 and the reagent used for the pH adjustment was acetic acid.

Subsequently 2-3 drops of termamyl were added to the gelatinized samples, stirred continuously and finally incubated at 100°C for 3mins to effect degradation of starch.

Neutrase incubation: Following the termamyl incubation, the pH of each sample was adjusted to 7.5. The adjustment of the pH was done by using 0.23M of Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and temperature reduced to 60°C; about 2-3 drops of neutrase enzyme was added to the samples stirred continuously and finally incubated at 60°C for 30mins to ensure complete removal of protein.

Amyloglucosidase incubation: Following the neutrase incubation, the pH of each sample contained in the beaker was further readjusted to 4.5. The pH adjustment was carried out by the use of acetic acid. The temperature of each beaker was maintained at 60°C and 2-3 drops of amyloglucosidase was added and stirred continuously. The AMG incubated was carried out at pH 4.5 for 30mins at 60°C. During incubation, there was continuous stirring to ensure complete hydrolysis of starch.

After the AMG incubation, the content in each beaker was washed samples were dried at 60-65°C for 5-6 hours to obtain the total dietary fibre.

$$\%TDF = \frac{\text{Weight of remaining dried mass (g)}}{\text{Weight of initial dried mass (g)}} \times 100$$

Soluble Dietary Fiber: The insoluble dietary fibers were obtained by precipitating the total dietary fibres with 4 volumes of ethanol, filtered and washed with ethanol and acetone. Subsequently, the

$$\%SDF = \frac{\text{Weight of dried mass of filtrate (g)}}{\text{Weight of TDF (g)}} \times 100$$

Insoluble Dietary Fiber

$$\%IDF = \frac{\text{Weight of dried mass of residue (g)}}{\text{Weight of TDF (g)}} \times 100$$

Flow chart for determination of total dietary fibre (TDF), insoluble dietary fibre (IDF) and soluble dietary fibre (SDF)

Determination of glyceimic (available) carbohydrate: Total carbohydrate of the samples will be determined by difference as described by Wolever et al (2003) and was calculated as;

$$\% \text{ glyceimic carbohydrate} = 100 - [a + b + c + d + e]$$

Where;

a= % moisture content

b= % ash content

c= % crude fat

d=%protein

e=%dietary fiber

Determination of Minerals: Mineral determination was done in line with AOAC (2015), 6g each of each sample was accurately weighed and the samples were introduced into a muffle furnace thermostated at 550⁰C until most of the organic matter was destroyed and a white- grey ash was obtained. The ash material was cooled. The analysis was carried out in two stages namely, preparation of ash and stock solutions. About 20 ml of distilled water and 10 ml of the dilute hydrochloric acid (HClO₄) was added to the ashed material. This mixture was boiled, filtered into a 250 ml volumetric flask, washed thoroughly with hot water, cooled and made up to volume. Stock solution of the elements was prepared by diluting the stock solution of the content which was boiled for 5min on a hot plate and placed in a fume cupboard.

Determination of Iron: 1.5 ml of extracted sample and 1.5 ml of prepared ash solution was taken in test tubes; containing 1.0 ml of 30% H₂SO₄ and 1.0 ml of 7% potassium per sulphate solution then 1.5 ml of 40% potassium thiocyanate solution are added. The red color developed was read at 540 nm within 20 minutes. The standard aliquots with concentration corresponding to 10- 50 µg were treated similarly. The estimation was done in triplicates and the results were expressed mg/100g sample.

Determination of Calcium: 2 ml of extracted sample and 2 ml of prepared ash solution in test tubes, added to 2.0 ml of distilled water and 1.0 ml of 4% ammonium oxalate, mixed well and allowed to stand overnight. After calcium precipitation, centrifuged and removed the supernatant fluid without disturbing the precipitate. To this 3.0 ml of 2% ~ 9 ~ of the Pharma Innovation Journal ammonia was added along the sides of the tube, mixed well and centrifuged again. Supernatant fluid was poured off. This was repeated until the supernatant gave no precipitate with calcium chloride solution. 2.0 ml of 1N H₂SO₄ was added and the precipitate was mixed well, then placed in boiling water bath for few minutes. Keeping the mixture at 70–75°C, and titrated against 0.01 N KMnO₄, to a faint pink color, which persisted for about a minute. It was also titrated against 2.0 ml of 1N H₂SO₄ as blank to the same endpoint. The difference between the titration gives the volume of 0.01N KMnO₄ recoded. The estimation was done in triplicates and the results were expressed mg/100g sample.

The 24- hour dietary recall: This is to obtain detailed information about all foods and beverages consumed on a given day. The 24-hr dietary recall method is widely used in general dietary assessment. This method employs trained interviewers to collect information on the dietary intake of respondents based on their memory (Ruel, 2003). The 24-hour dietary recall (24HR) is a structured interview intended to capture detailed information about all foods and beverages consumed by the respondent in the past 24 hours, most commonly, from midnight to midnight the previous day. A key feature of the 24HR is that, when appropriate, the respondent is asked for more detailed information than first reported. For example, a respondent reporting chicken for dinner or a sandwich for lunch would be asked about the preparation method and type of bread, (Daniels, Adair, Popkin and Truong, 2009).

This open-ended response structure is designed to prompt respondents to provide a comprehensive and detailed report of all foods and beverages consumed. In addition to other detailed information, such as time of day and source of food, portion size of each food and beverage is captured. Food models, pictures, and other visual aids were used to help respondents judge and report portion size and may improve accuracy (Daniels, *et.al.*, 2009).

The food intake data of the respondents were collected by caregiver single 24-hour food recall. The interviews included a description of the foods eaten, the cooking method and names of foods eaten (e.g. for milk consumed or other processed snack foods). Respondents provided descriptions of food and beverages consumed. Questions were also asked to prompt the respondent to remember anything omitted in the list and included questions on the specific food groups.

Dietary diversity (DD)

Dietary diversity (DD) is defined as the number of different foods or food groups consumed in the previous day. It is a qualitative measure of food consumption that reflects household access to a variety of foods, and is also an assessment for nutrient adequacy of the diet of individuals (WHO, 2018). The data collected from the 24hour recall can be analyzed to provide information on specific food groups eaten. It is an indicator of a diet's nutrient adequacy (FAO, 2010).

Dietary diversity score (DDS): The diversity of the respondent's diet was graded as very low, when less than 4 food groups were consumed, low when 5 food groups were consumed, medium when 6 food groups were consumed and high when more than 7 food groups were consumed

Calculation of dietary diversity score:

The dietary diversity was assessed from the 24hours dietary recall. It was done by summing the number of food groups consumed during the past 24hours as shown below.

Dietary diversity score

DD <4 food	Low DD 5 food (groups)	Medium DD 6 food (groups)	High DD >7 food groups
Cereals	Cereals	Cereals	Cereals (pastas, rice, bread)
Fish and sea foods (crayfish, oysters, prawns)	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables	Vit. A rich Fruits and Vegetables
Milk and milk products	Fish and sea foods prawn, (crayfish, oysters)	Sugar/sweets (sweets, sweeteners, sugars)	Root and Tubers (yam, cocoyam, potatoes, etc)
Meat and Poultry	Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts, nuts)	Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts)	Fish and sea foods, prawn (crayfish, oysters)
	Meat and poultry	Oils/Fats (butter, palm oil margarine, vegetable)	Milk and Milk Products
	Oils	Milk and Milk Products	Beverages
		Fish and sea foods (crayfish, oysters, prawns)	Meat/Poultry
		Root and Tubers (yam, cocoyam, potatoes, etc)	Sugar/sweets (sweets, sweeteners, sugars)
			Oils/Fats (butter, margarine, vegetable & palm oils)
			Pulses/Legumes/Nuts (Beans, pea nuts, nuts)
		Eggs	

RESULTS

• **Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Children within Five Years in the three camps**

The research was carried out on 1,420 (100%) children of 6 to 59 months who were the target age range. From table 1, it was observed that 280 (20%) were less than 12 months of age, majority of the children 728 (51%) were between 12 to 36 months, 412 (29%) were between 37 to 59 months of age. 813 (57.3%) were male, while 607 (42.7%) were female. 410 (29%) were born as first children of the family while 1,010 (71%) were 2nd to 4th born children of the family. 159 (11%) are the first and only children of the family, 994 (70%) were born in less than two years interval between other siblings while 267 (19%) were born in more than two years interval between other siblings. 504 (35%) were delivered at the health facilities while 916 (65%) were delivered at home.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Children within Five Years in New Kuchingoro IDP Camp Abuja, Bakasi Camp Borno, and Bakassi Camp Bayelsa

Variables (Number of children =1420)	Frequency	%
Age (months)	(n)	100
<12	280	20
12-36	728	51
37-59mths	412	29
Gender		
Male	813	57.3
Female	607	42.7
Birth order		
1 st	410	29
2-4	1,010	71
Birth interval		
1 st and only child	159	11
<2 years	994	70
≥2 years	267	19
Place of delivery		
Health facility	504	35
Home	916	65

- **The 24hour Dietary Recall of the 1,420 preschool children**

Table 2 presents the 24-hour dietary recall of the respondents. Analysis of the 24-hour dietary recall of the caregivers indicates that 385 (58.7%) of the respondents ate cereals, within the specified 24hrs, 500 (35.1%) ate roots and tubers, 685 (48.1%) ate fruits and vegetables. 154 (10.4%) ate meat and poultry, 54 (13.4%) ate eggs, while 158 (11.1%) ate fish and sea foods, 71 (4.9%) ate pulses/legumes/nuts, while 75 (3.2%) ate milk and milk products, 87 (6.1%) consumed oils while 235 (16.4%) consumed sugar

Table 2: The 24hour Dietary Recall of the 1,420 preschool children

Food Groups	Males	Females	Total
Cereals	401 (28.2%)	434 (30.5%)	385 (58.7%)
Root and Tubers	254 (17.8%)	246 (17.3%)	500 (35.1%)
Vegetables/Fruits	345 (24.2%)	340 (23.9%)	685 (48.1%)
Meat/Poultry	76 (5%)	78 (5.4%)	154 (10.4%)
Eggs	20 (1%)	34 (2.4%)	54 (13.4%)
Fish and sea foods	78 (5.5%)	80 (5.6%)	158 (11.1%)
Pulses/Legumes/Nuts	34 (2.3%)	37 (2.6%)	71 (4.9%)
Milk and Milk Products	35 (2.4%)	40 (2.8%)	75 (3.2%)
Oils/Fats	43 (3.0 %)	44 (3.1%)	87 (6.1%)
Sugar	101 (7.0%)	134 (9.4 %)	235 (16.4%)

- **Diversity of the preschool children’s diet**

Table 3 indicates the diversity of the 1,420 preschools diets. Analysis of the table shows that 441 (31.0%) preschool children consumed less than 4 food groups in 24 hours, while 509 (35.8%) consumed 5 food groups, 446 (31.4%) of the respondents consumed 6 food groups, while 24 (1.6%) consumed more than more than 7 food groups.

Table 3: Diversity of the preschool children’s diet

Diversity Score	Male		Females		Total	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
< 4 (Very Low)	218	15.3%	223	15.7%	441	31.0%
5 (Low)	252	17.7%	257	18.1%	509	35.8%
6 (Medium)	208	14.6%	238	16.7%	446	31.4%
> 7 (High)	10	0.7%	14	0.9%	24	1.6%
Total	688	48.5%	732	51.5%	1,420	100%

- **Mean Nutrient Present in Each Food Sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 1: Mean Nutrient Present in each food sample, from the chart, there is 62.03 moisture, 2.52 Ash, 1.08 Dietary fiber, 6.81 fat, 6.39 protein, 21.19 carbon, 0.05 iron, 3.36 calcium and 181.36 energy

- **Nutrient composition of sample EGS (Egusi Soup) in percentage presented in a pie chart**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 2: Nutrient composition of sample EGS (Egusi soup) in percentage presented in a pie chart. When the egusi soup when analyzed, it was noted to contain 65% of moisture, 3% of calcium, 13% of carbohydrate, 6% protein, 6% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 6% ash and 0% iron

EGS – Egusi soup; YPS – Yam Pepper Soup; IDM – Indomie ; JER – Jollof Rice; TSS – Tuwo Shinkafa
 CYS – Cocoyam soup; OGS – Ogbolo Soup; FGN – Fara du nunu; BEP – Beans Pottage; WRS – White Rice

- Nutrient composition of sample YPS in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 3: Nutrient composition of sample YPS in percentage presented in a pie chart, containing 72% moisture, 2% calcium, 8% carbohydrate, 5% protein, 7% fat, 2% dietary fiber, 4% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample IDM (Indomie) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 4: Nutrient composition of sample IDM (Indomie) in percentage presented in a pie chart, containing 52% moisture, 1% calcium, 32% carbohydrate, 5% protein, 7% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample JER (Jollof Rice) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 5: Nutrient composition of sample JER (Jollof Rice) in percentage presented in a pie chart, containing 62% moisture, 4% calcium, 18% carbohydrate, 5% protein, 9% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 1% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample TSS (Tuwo shinkafa) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 6: Nutrient composition of sample TSS (Tuwo shinkafa) in percentage presented in a pie chart, containing 78% moisture, 4% calcium, 6% carbohydrate, 4% protein, 5% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample CYS (Cocoyam soup) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 7: Nutrient composition of sample CYS (cocoyam) in percentage presented in a pie chart, containing 44% moisture, 5% calcium, 39% carbohydrate, 6% protein, 3% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample OGS (Ogbolo Soup) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Table 8: Nutrient composition of sample OGS (Ogbolo Soup) in percentage presented in a pie chart, contains 49% moisture, 4% calcium, 31% carbohydrate, 7% protein, 6% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample FDN (Fara du nuu) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 9: Nutrient composition of sample FDN (Fara du nuu) in percentage presented in a pie chart, contains 63% moisture, 3% calcium, 16% carbohydrate, 10% protein, 6% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 1% ash and 0% iron

- **Figure 10** Nutrient composition of sample BEP (Beans Pottage) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 10 Nutrient composition of sample BEP (Beans Pottage) in percentage presented in a pie chart, contains 46% moisture, 4% calcium, 30% carbohydrate, 9% protein, 8% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Nutrient composition of sample WRS (White Rice) in percentage presented in a pie chart

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 11: Nutrient composition of sample WRS (White Rice) in percentage presented in a pie chart, contains 68% moisture, 3% calcium, 12% carbohydrate, 6% protein, 8% fat, 1% dietary fiber, 2% ash and 0% iron

- Composition of ASH in 100gm of each food sample

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 12: Composition of ASH in 100gm of each food sample, EGS contain 6.69 ash, YPS contain 3.78, IDM contains 1.62 ash, JER contain 1.62, TSS 2.27, CYS 2.19, OGS 2.21, FDN 1.24, BEP 2.03 while WRS contain 1.53

- **Composition of protein in 100gm of each food sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 13: Composition of protein in 100gm of each food sample, EGS contain 5.95 protein, 5.6 protein in YPS, 4.55 protein in IDM, 5.25 in JER, 3.65 in TSS, 5.95 in CYC, 7 protein in OGS, 10.15 in FDN, 9.45 in BEP and 6.3 in WRS

- **Composition of Carbohydrate in 10gm of each food sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 14: Composition of Carbohydrate in 10gm of each food sample, the food materials contain the following – EGS 3.29 Carbohydrate, 7.99 in YPS, 2.69 in IDM, 9.14 in JER, 6.53 in TSS, 10.65 in CYC, 1.83 in OGS, 6.43 in FDN, 31.37 in BEP and 1.96 in WRS

- **Composition of Iron in 100gm of each food sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 15: Composition of Iron in 100gm of each food sample, contain 0.021 iron in EGS, 0.179 in YPS, 0.011 in IDM, 0.034 in JER, 0.014 in TSS, 0.011 in CYS, 0.196 in OGS, 0.021 in FDN, 0.038 in BEP and 0.009 in WRS

- **Composition of calcium in 100gm of each food sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 16: Composition of calcium in 100gm of each food sample, contain 2.78 calcium in EGS (1), 1.78 in YPS (2), 1.48 in IDM (3), 3.78 in JER (4), 4.28 in TSS (5), 5.28 in CYS (6), 4.09 in OGS (7), 3.08 in FDN (8), 3.48 in BEP (9) and 3.56 in WRS (10)

- **Composition of energy (calorie) in 100gm of each food sample**

Measured in, Iron (mg), Calcium (mg), Energy (kcal), Protein (g), Fat (g), Carbohydrate (g), Dietary fiber (g), Ash (g)

Figure 17: Composition of energy in 100gm of each food sample, contain 42.88 calorie in EGS, 27.45 in YPS, 27.06 in IDM, 87.33 in JER, 23.99 in TSS, 30.61 in CYS, 26.47 in OGS, 71.34 in FDN, 48.12 in BEP and 58.39 in WRS

- **Composition of nutrients, moisture and energy in all the food samples**

Figure 18: Is the summary of the composition of nutrients, moisture and energy in all the food samples in a graphic presentation

DISCUSSION

- **Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Children within Five Years in the three IDP camps**

The socio-demographic characteristics of the under-five children observed that majority of the children were between 12 to 36 months (they make up 51% of the sample population) with only 20% of them being below a year. There are more male (57%) than female (47%) children within the age bracket used for this study at the camps. A recent study carried out by (Perjan, Carolina, Sanduleac and Sergiu, 2018) reported that for all macronutrient, sex (gender) difference was significant in nutrition. More than half (62%) of the children were between 2nd and 4th in birth order (2nd, 3rd or 4th child of their parents), with only 15% been the first children from their homes. This suggests that 85% of the families in the IDP camps had more than one child with over 23% of them having at least 5 children.

- **Food Analysis and Dietary Diversity**

- **Moisture Content**

The result of moisture content of the food samples is seen in table 4.1. Cocoyam soup (CYS) had the least moisture content (46.40 ± 1.95) while Tuwo shinkafa & Sauce (TSS) has the highest moisture content (81.59 ± 4.29). The moisture content of a food influences the quality such as taste, appearance, texture, flavor (organoleptic qualities), the nutritive properties, and shelf life. This may therefore affect the way they enjoyed the food and by extension, the quantity that the children may eat. This might result in self-inflicted malnutrition. All the samples in this study had high moisture content ($46.40 \pm 1.59 - 4.29$) which suggests that they will likely have a low keeping dry matter (nutrient). Considering the fact that resources like refrigerator are limited in the camps, the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) may be feeding on food that are high on microbes when the foods are not consumed immediately, they are cooked as the high moisture contents makes them susceptible to microbial attack. According to the FAO (2022), a long-term exposure to such food can affect the immune system. It reported that an estimated 600 million – almost 1 in every 10 people in the world fall ill after eating contaminated foods and 420 die every year, leading to the loss of 33 million lives yearly. It can therefore be asserted that the high moisture content of the foods served to the IDPs in the camps may inadvertently have contributed to the death of some of them, as it promotes the growth of foodborne diseases. According to Havelaar, Kirk, Torgerson, Gibb, Hald, Lake, Praet, Bellinger, De Silva and Gargouri, (2015), the common microorganism that are prevalent and responsible for foodborne diseases and intoxication in Nigeria are *Escherichia coli* 0157:H7, *Salmonella shigella* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and these organisms thrive very well at moisture contents above 16%. This implies that all the foods used in this study are likely to be potential source of foodborne disease in the IDPs camp in Nigeria and if the foods are not eaten in time may have an adverse effect on the health of IDPs with implications such as loss of productivity and low quality of life.

- **Ash Content**

According to Trumbo, Schlicker, Yates a Poos, (2002), the ash content of the food samples represents the total mineral in foods. From the result obtained, the egusi soup (EGS) has the highest mineral content while the 'Fara du nunu' (FDN) had the least minerals. The difference in the mineral contents of the foods differs significantly. This notwithstanding, it may not be possible to state which food is richer than the other as the result is not qualitative but quantitative because the individual constituents of the minerals were not identified in this work. However, the result of ash in the Egusi soup in this study compares favourably with what was obtained by Trumbo, *et.al.*, (2002). The ash contents of the indomie (IDM), yam pepper soup (YPS), Jellof rice (JER), Tuwo shinkafa & sauce (TSS) and bean pottage with crayfish (BEP) were higher

than what was obtainable by Ejembi, Snni, Emmanuel, Friday and Abbah, (2014), the ash contents of the cocoyam soup (CYS), ogbolo soup (OGS), white rice (WRS) and 'Fura de nunu' (FDN) were less than what was obtained by Liao, Wang, Tseng, Chen, Lin and Chen, (2004). The indomie and jollof rice had the same apparent value (1.62g/100g) which suggest that the quantitative value of minerals obtained from both foods is the same.

➤ **Dietary Fibre**

The dietary content of the food samples obtained from the IDP camps are seen in table 4.1. The dietary fibre ranged from $0.48 \pm 0.04\text{g}/100\text{g}$ to $2.43 \pm 0.16\text{g}/100\text{g}$. Yam pepper soup (YPS) had the highest dietary fibre content while Tuwo shincafa sauce (TSS) had the least. The samples had significant differences in the quantity of dietary fibres per 100g. According to (Veronese, Solmi, Caruso, Giannelli, Osella and Evangelou, 2018), dietary fibres are mainly indigestible carbohydrates and therefore, the high dietary fibre in the yam pepper soup may have been an indication that the yam itself may have a higher amount of indigestible carbohydrate compared to any other food analysed in this study. Veronese, *et.al.*, (2018) reported a relatively high amount of dietary fibre in three-leved yam (*Discerea domentorum*) and aerial yam (*Discerea bulbifera*) with values ranging from 2.17 ± 0.08 to 2.99 ± 0.34 and 2.05 ± 0.22 to 2.71 ± 0.19 respectively. Institute of Medicine, (2005) asserts that over 83 percent of the dietary fibre in yam is composed mainly of insoluble dietary fibre fraction. According to Coudray, Demigné and Rayssiguier, (2003), this fraction of dietary fibre promotes the movement of materials through the digestive system and increase stool bulk, making one to feel full for long. These may be a way that hunger is controlled in the camp even with small feeding. With this strategy, the children are more likely to eat little and remain filled for a longer period of time. Thus, hunger is controlled. The least dietary fibre value recorded for TSS is indicative that it will be high in available (glycemic) carbohydrate content. This implies that it will be a major source of energy food in the camp and will likely be consumed mainly by children in the IDP camp because of its high digestibility, (Coudray, *et.al.*, 2003).

➤ **Fat content**

The fat in the foods collected from the IDP camps can were between 3.13 ± 0.11 and 9.05 ± 0.29 . Jollof rice (JER) had the highest values while CYS (Cocoyam soup) had the least. The fat content of the jollof rice may be as a result of the oil used in cooking, Trumbo, *et.al.*, (2002) had reported during her explanation of high fat content of jollof rice that most women do not only use groundnut oil to fry their tomatoes used in making the stew for jollof rice but also add red (palm) oil in order to make it very red, especially when tomatoes is costly. This may be the same reason for the high fat content of the jollof rice in the IDP camps as it was observed that the cost of tomatoes at the time of visit was quite expensive and the power supply to the camp was erratic thus reducing the likelihood that the tomatoes could be purchased in large quantities at a cheaper rate & then stored for a long-time use. The implication of the high fat content in the jollof rice could be due the addition of excess oil simply implies that it may not be too healthy for the children. Hu, Dam and Liu, (2001) reported that palm oil is high in saturated fatty acids. According to Ji, & Chen, (2013), in adipose tissue obesity leads to infiltration of maicrophoges that secrete pro-inflammatory cytokines that inhibit insulin signaling by phosphorylating serine residues of IRS protein. On the contrary, Siri-Tarino, Sun, Hu and Krauss (2010) reported that healthy mono-saturated fats are more effective in preventing cardiovascular mortality and commonly artery disease than low-fat, low-cholesterol diets. From the results obtained in this study, EGS and YSP had the same fat content (that is not statistically significant) in the same way, BEP and WRS, OGS and FDN also have statistically equal fat content. It is therefore important to mention that the

fat content (mass per sample) may not be the issue but the nature of the fats in the foods. The fat content is better of the oil source are basically of the mono-saturated form rather than the unsaturated form.

➤ **The 24-hour dietary recall of the preschool children:**

The 24-hour dietary recall revealed that 58.7% of the preschool children ate cereals, 31.6% ate fruits and vegetables, (35.1%) consumed roots and tubers and (10.4%) consumed meat and poultry within the last 24hours. These foods are readily available in the locality and are good sources of protein, vitamins and minerals. USDA MyPlate & Food Pyramid Resources, (2013), stated that meat, poultry and fish supply protein, iron and zinc. It is necessary to consume 2 to 3 servings of protein rich foods daily and proteins are essential for the growth and repair of body cells to provides energy in the absence of carbohydrates and when eaten in excess is converted to fat (Sun, Schutz, Maffeis and Obes, (2004). Also, 3.2% of the preschool children consumed milk and milk products, while 11.1% consumed fish and sea foods and 16.4% consumed sugar, the consumption of vegetables and fruits is a good practice and should be encouraged. Fruits and vegetables are rich in vitamins and minerals and is necessary in the diet for good health, they are essential to maintain healthy tissues, necessary for cell respiration, help in the absorption of nutrients, promotion of growth, help boost immunity (Baeke, Takiishi, Korf, Gysemans and Mathieu, 2010). But the percentage of preschool children who consumed the above food groups are minimal, making it possible for the children to be malnourished. Eating variety of fruits and vegetables every day, with every meal and different colors provide different benefits to the nutritional status of an individual (Baeke, *et.al.*, 2010).

➤ **Diversity of the preschool diet:**

The table above indicates that the diversity of the 1,420 preschools children's diets shows that 441 (31.0%) preschool children consumed less than 4 food groups in 24 hours, while 509 (35.8%) consumed 5 food groups, 446 (31.4%) of the respondents consumed 6 food groups, while 24 (1.6%) consumed more than more than 7 food groups. Inadequate dietary diversity is a problem among the preschool children. A case study by Gregory, McCullough, Ramirez-Zea and Stein, (2008), in an urban area in Mali, revealed that cereal consumption was 100% and almost all other food group consumption was low. But their animal food consumption was poor. This condition may be due to their daily consumption of rice-based diet with few other food commodities. A dietary intake assessment by (Neves and Madruga, 2019) stated that the diversity involving few food groups is poor. Eating food from more food groups provides an adequate diet and is necessary for proper growth and development in the lives of the preschools. It is also vital in the effort to combat malnutrition. When the children do not get all the nutrients needed for growth and development, it deteriorates their health, (Neves and Madruga, 2019),

CONCLUSION

This study highlighted high prevalence of inadequate food supply in the IDP Camps in Nigeria which requires urgent action. High-protein foods were not well consumed and a majority of children did not meet the recommended minimum dietary diversity. Findings from the study also show a large proportion of preschool children had low dietary diversity score and most of them consumed cereals. Household food insecurity prevalence was high, which may be linked to the low dietary intake leading to malnutrition. (Rammohan, Pritchard and Dibley, (2019). This needs an urgent intervention to improve preschool children dietary diversity in IDP camps through food security interventions, female empowerment and nutrition education programs in the camps.

Recommendations

- There should be interventions that focus on improving the food security and socioeconomic status of the IDPs to give social support
- Governments and non-governmental organizations should provide care for those in IDP camps and pay special efforts to improve the dietary diversity and nutritional status of children.
- There should be urgent intervention to provide food to support preschool children diet in IDP camps through food security interventions, female empowerment and nutrition education programs in the camps.

Limitations experienced in the study

- The food samples collected from the caregivers on behalf of the preschool children may not be a true representation of all similar IDP Camps in the country.
- Most of the caregivers refused to release their food samples for analysis
- The camps represented in this study may not be true representation of all the IDP camps in the country
- The security risks limited our movements round the camps
- It was difficult to convince some caregivers about the study and to release their food samples.
- Financial constraints on the researcher
- There was incomplete information of the 24HR leading to potential bias

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